

GENERAL INFORMATION AND PSYCHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF FAIRY TALE THERAPY

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Abstract. *In this article, reliance on genuine national values is increasingly being established in the education system, and the approach to the upbringing of the soul, that is, the formation of human spirituality, as a primary task is becoming a priority. Therefore, if attention is paid to the spiritual upbringing of the younger generation from a young age, it will bear great fruit. In order to instill love and enthusiasm for books in our children, first of all, we ourselves must have the right attitude towards them. Children are considered a magical world, living in a period of rapid growth, development and change. This is another proof of how important this period is in raising children. Today, psychologists are increasingly emphasizing fairy tale therapy as one of the methods of raising children. Fairy tale therapy is a method of raising and treating children through fairy tales.*

Keywords: *Fairy tale therapy, psychological research, fairy tales, psychological knowledge, spirituality, education, upbringing.*

ERTAKTERAPIYA HAQIDA UMUMIY MA'LUMOTLAR VA PSIXOLOGIK TAHLILI

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada ta'lim-tarbiya tizimida asl milliy qadriyatlarga asoslangan tarbiyasiga, ya'ni inson ma'naviyatini shakllantirishga birlamchi vazifa sifatida yondashish ustuvor bo'lib bormoqda. Binobarin, yosh avlodni yoshligidan ma'naviyatli qilib tarbiyalashga e'tibor berib borilsa, u o'zining katta samarasini beradi. Bolalarimizda kitobga mehr, ishtiyoq uyg'otish uchun, avvalo, o'zimiz unga to'g'ri munosabatda bo'lishimiz lozim. Bolalar ohangraboli olam hisoblanib juda tez o'sish, rivojlanish va o'zgarishlar ichida yashaydilar. Bu farzand tarbiyasida aynan shu palla qanchalik ahamiyatli ekanining yana bir*

isbotidir. Bugungi kun psixologlari bolalarni tarbiyalashning usullaridan biri sifatida ertak terapiyani juda ko'p ta'kidlab o'tishmoqda. Ertakterapiya bu bolani ertaklar orqali tarbiyalash va davolash metodidir.

Kalit so'zlar: Ertakterapiya, psixologik tadqiqotlar, ertak, psixologik bilimlar, ma'naviyat, ta'lim, tarbiya.

ОБЩАЯ ИНФОРМАЦИЯ И ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ СКАЗКОТЕРАПИИ

Аннотация. В статье утверждается, что в системе образования все больше утверждается опора на подлинные национальные ценности, и что первостепенной задачей становится подход к воспитанию души, то есть формированию духовности человека. Поэтому, уделяя внимание духовному воспитанию подрастающего поколения с юных лет, можно добиться больших результатов. Чтобы привить детям любовь и страсть к книгам, мы должны прежде всего сами правильно к ним относиться. Дети считаются хрупким миром, живущим в мире быстрого роста, развития и перемен. Это еще одно доказательство того, насколько важен этот период в воспитании ребенка.

Современные психологи выделяют сказкотерапию как один из методов воспитания детей. Сказкотерапия — метод обучения и лечения детей посредством сказок.

Ключевые слова: Сказкотерапия, психологические исследования, сказки, психологические знания, духовность, образование, воспитание.

Introduction

Fairy tales have an active effect on both the mind and the heart, filling the mind, making the heart emotional. We all want our children to grow up brave and ambitious, pious, faithful, intelligent. To do this, we can use fairy tales that have a positive effect on their upbringing and develop their mental potential. Fairy tale therapy is a method used to improve interaction with the environment and correct emotional disorders. Fairy tales give hope to a child. The more a child believes in Santa Claus, who brings gifts on New Year's Eve, the more optimistic he looks at life. Through fairy tales, we educate a child, enrich his inner world, heal his soul, give him knowledge about life, and develop his imagination. The main sign of a true fairy tale is its good ending. This gives the child a sense of psychological protection. Whatever happens in fairy tales, it ends well, all the trials that befall the heroes of the fairy tale make them stronger and wiser.

On the other hand, the child sees that the heroes who committed bad deeds will certainly be punished for their deeds. He is sure that the heroes who successfully passed all the trials and showed all their positive qualities will certainly be rewarded. Then the main law of life becomes clear: the way you treat life, it will respond to you in the same way. Korney Ivanovich Chikovskiy wrote: "I think the purpose of a fairy tale is to educate in a child some kind of humanity, such as the ability to grieve for someone else's sorrow, to rejoice for someone else's joy, to experience the fate of a stranger as if it were his own." Note that this is about two people understanding each other, caring for each other. Fairy tales have been used in their work by world psychologists such as E. Fromm, E. Berne, E. Gordner, I. V. Vajkov, M. Osorina, E. Lisina. From fairy tales, children gain their first ideas about justice and injustice. A fairy tale forces a child to keep in mind and ponder the ways of solving complex life problems. In this case, the experience of the collision of opposing forces in life and their resolution increases, and creative imagination develops. It is imagination combined with memory that allows a child to find the right and effective solution in a short time when faced with similar problems in life. A fairy tale is life itself, reflecting the actions of heroes in unprecedented situations, but instilling in the child's memory and mind the understanding that even the most basic, sometimes seemingly impossible, difficult situations still have a solution. There are no dead ends in life. Often a person is simply not ready to get out of them. What does fairy tale therapy give a child? With the help of fairy tale therapy, imagination, creative imagination develop, and peace of mind is achieved. The child learns to analyze the actions of others and apply this knowledge in his own actions.

Through group discussion, communicative contact is established between participants.

Fairy tale therapy also helps adults overcome their phobias and fears, reduces their aggressiveness and anxiety. Through fairy tales, we can reveal and solve problems in the child's soul. Such fairy tales are called therapeutic fairy tales. Often, fairy tales are told in the evening before going to bed, because at this time the child is calm, and this is a convenient time to influence him. Therefore, in the evening, it is necessary to tell fairy tales with a positive meaning that end with goodness. Also, fairy tales listened to in the family circle, with the discussion of adults, create a basis for solving the problem and correcting it. Fairy tales raise a child. First of all, it is necessary to tell a fairy tale to a child willingly, then the child will get more from folk art. If the child is mentally calm during the fairy tale telling process, and the environment is calm, the effect will be better. When telling a fairy tale to a child, you can ask him the following questions: Fairy tales for children develop their imagination, logical and figurative thinking, and

develop their speech. Fairy tales reduce anxiety and increase self-confidence. N.L. Kryajeva suggests telling the fairy tale about the “Fisherman and the Fish” to timid children, the fairy tale about the “Cowardly Rabbits” to gullible children, “The Adventures of Pinocchio” to stubborn children, and the fairy tales “The Princess and the Pea” and “Puss in Boots” to restless children.

Tales with a similar content are also found among our Uzbek folk tales. The tale "Zumrad va Qimmat" fights against frivolity and laziness in children, the tale "Ur toqmoq" fights against deceit, and the tale "Susambil" fights against unruliness. Many more such examples can be given. All tales have educational value and sow the seeds of goodness in the child's heart. It is more appropriate for parents to tell their children fairy tales rather than read them. Because this allows parents to observe how their beloved reacts to the fairy tale. In addition, parents travel to the world of fairy tales with their children, which is better than if the child travels to them alone.

Children have the ability to better perceive images described by others. Therefore, when telling your child a fairy tale, try to describe all the scenes in it. Give your child the opportunity to choose the fairy tale himself. If he wants to hear about "Little Red Riding Hood" ten times, it's not in vain. This fairy tale is contributing something to the formation of his consciousness, some process is taking place in it. Another important rule is not to explain the deep meaning of a fairy tale to a child. Otherwise, the fairy tale will die - it will lose its significance and there will be no benefit from it. It is necessary to avoid making corrections and changes to folk tales, especially those related to real life. These changes will make it difficult for the child to accept the world of fairy tales. The goal and task of fairy tale therapy is to eliminate aggressiveness in children, develop emotional self-control and positive relationships with others. For this, fairy tale therapy uses a fairy tale style and ways of working with children that are understandable to them due to their simplicity and interest in fairy tales. Each child understands and perceives a fairy tale in his own way. That is why one fairy tale leaves a great impression on him, while another passes by without stirring up his emotions. In fairy tales aimed at correcting negative emotional changes in behavior, it is not a deep understanding of the plot, but the relationship between people, their heroic deeds, the outcome of this or that choice, their personal attitude to a particular situation, their connection with their personal life through events and heroic deeds, which is in the heart of the person listening and reading. This must be taken into account, because in many cases parents attribute their personal fears to the child's fears. Like the fear of life, the fear of death is characteristic not only of children, but, on the contrary, more of parents than of children.

At the same time, it is the fear of not finding one's place in life, the fear of losing one's spouse, the fear of family breakdown, the fear of not gaining respect at work... These are our fears, you and I, and they should not be considered our children's.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that emotional disorders in a child's behavior can, of course, be corrected with the help of games, toys, the child's visual activity, music, theater, and art in general. However, the most understandable and favorite method for children is a fairy tale. With the help of a correctly selected fairy tale, many problems in a child - fear, capriciousness, etc. - are eliminated, and the child develops determination and willpower. Using fairy tales not only in psychological therapy, but also regularly in the family circle, allows you to imprint the warmest feelings of childhood in the child's memory. Fairy tales should be composed based on the child's problems, and during fairy tale therapy, each child's behavior should be given importance. Based on the individual characteristics of the child, it is necessary to regularly monitor the level of acceptance of the fairy tale.

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